

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17670453

Achieving Energy Security In Africa

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ABSTRACT

This paper is an attempt to explore Africa's energy security and ways of achieving energy supply. It was found that Africa as a continent is energy rich with abundance of natural resources conserve and enhance reliable, affordable, available and sustainable energy supply to domestic users. That Africa has other means to sustain energy such as coal, natural gas, oil and gas, uranium and renewable energies. However, Africa is faced with challenges such as high debts, mismanagement of utilities, corruption, over dependence on imported fuels etc. This work looked at some of the legal and institutional frameworks in Africa propelling the drive for energy security and supply. In summary it is evident that Africa has undermined and underutilized her natural resources that is meant to carter her energy demands. This paper recommends that Africa should leverage on natural gas, collaboration with States, create friendly policy framework, build human and improve accountability and transparency.

Keywords: Energy security, security of supply, petroleum

1.0. INTRODUCTION

Energy has been and will continue to be a factor advancing the human world and society. That is, from its daily living, to commercial activities and to development. It is therefore crucial for both human growth, development and sustainability. Africa is the most energy-deficient continent in the world, as it hosts 75 percent of the world's population without access to electricity.³ Energy security in Africa is going concern to the continent and it is of great importance knowing that the continent is buoyant with energy resources and should be optimal in energy security. Africa is energy paradox- she is rich in energy resources but poor in energy security supply. Just like Nigeria, she is more of a gas nation than oil. Africa's uranium reserves have inspired a new extractive investment boom. This examines foreign powers' efforts to enhance their energy security through increased exploitation of Sub-Saharan Africa's energy resources and the implications of these activities for energy security within Africa.⁴

According to Gary and Karl, the Gulf of Guinea is one of the few areas of the world that is still believed to contain large-scale undiscovered reservoirs of light sweet crude.⁵ That is to say Africa still has lots of untapped natural resource areas to enhance the efficiency of energy security and supply in Africa. it is the availability of diverse energy resources, sustainable in quantities, affordable in prices, that supports economic growth, assists in poverty alleviation, does not harm the environment and considers disruptions and shocks.

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³ Gracelin Baskaran and Sophie Coste, 'Achieving Universal Energy Access in Africa amid Global Decarbonization.' <https://www.csis.org/analysis/achieving-universal-energy-access-africa-amid-global-decarbonization>

⁴ Emily Meierding, "Energy Security and Sub-Saharan Africa", *International Development Policy | Revue internationale de politique de développement* [Online], 2 | 2011, Online since 14 February 2013, connection on 27 October 2024. URL: <http://journals.openedition.org/poldev/744>; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4000/poldev.744>

⁵ Gary, I. and T.L. Karl (2003) *Bottom of the Barrel: Africa's Oil Boom and the Poor* (Baltimore: Catholic Relief Services).

According to the Sustainable Development Goal 7 tracking report, Africa is unlikely to meet the SDG7 targets. To achieve its energy and climate goals, Africa needs \$190 billion of investment a year between 2026 and 2030, with two-thirds of this going to clean energy, the International Energy Agency (IEA)⁶

2.0. Definition of terms

2.1. Petroleum

The word petroleum comes from the Greek word *Petra* meaning rock and the Greek word *elaion* meaning oil. In the nineteenth century, the term petroleum was frequently used to refer to mineral oils produced by distillation from mined organic solids such as cannel coal and later oil shale, and refined oils produced from them.

Petroleum is a naturally occurring yellow-to-black liquid found in the geologic formations beneath the earth's surface, which is commonly refined into various types of fuels. It consists of hydrocarbons of various molecular weights and other liquid organic compounds. The name petroleum covers both naturally occurring unprocessed crude oil and petroleum products that are made up. Petroleum is a liquid substance that is found in rock formation.⁷

Geologically, petroleum along with the natural combustible mineral deposits are called fossil fuel. Fossil fuels include coal, natural gas and petroleum (also known as oil or called crude oil), which are petrified and liquefied remains of millions of years accumulation of decayed plant life.⁸

According to Omorogbe, 'petroleum is a compound mainly composed of hydrogen and carbon, and is commonly called a hydrocarbon. It can exist in gaseous, liquid or solid form. When it is found as a solid, it is coal, shale, tar, sands, or bitumen. In liquid form, it is referred to as crude oil. Hydrocarbons in gaseous form are known as natural gas'.⁹

The term petroleum is generally used for the liquid form and commonly called crude oil. The term oil is loosely used to refer to petroleum and, in many cases, giving the same meaning with crude oil.

2.2. Energy Security

Over time, there have been no single accepted definition but there has been an evolution of the definition of energy security. Energy security refers to a situation of availability, reliability, affordability, accessibility and sustainability of energy resources in the absence of foreign constraints. The ability to access energy in a reliable and affordable manner.

OECD summarized energy supply at the government to be the availability of sufficient supplies at affordable prices.

According to International Energy Agency, energy insecurity stems from the welfare impact of either the physical unavailability of energy, or prices that are not competitive or overtly volatile.¹⁰ It is a condition in which the nation and citizens and business have access to sufficient energy resources at a reasonable price for a foreseeable future free from risk of disruption of services.

To Elkind, it is availability (Physical endowment, capital investment, structure), reliability (extent of services without interruption), affordability (transparent prices) and sustainability (energy system and infrastructure do not promote climate change).¹¹

Energy security is the situation where there is the accessibility, availability, affordability and sustainability of energy without any form of restriction of all forms. The security of the supply of energy can be enhanced through the development of renewables which is equally a cleaner alternative to fossil fuel.

⁶ O Douglas, 'Energy: Africa's stand at COP27' <https://www.un.org/africarenewal/magazine/november-2022/energy-africas-stand-cop27> accessed 28th October, 2025; <https://www.iea.org/reports/africa-energy-outlook-2022/key-findings>

⁷ A U Kyuka, 'Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry Laws: Policies and Institutions (Malthouse Press Limited) xxvii

⁸ J R McNeil, 'Environmental Effects of the Fossil Fuel Age'

⁹ O Yinka 'Oil and Gas Law in Nigeria', (Malthouse Law Books, 2001) 1

¹⁰ OECD/IEA, Energy Security and Climate Change Policy: Assessing Interactions (OECD/IEA 2007) 35.

¹¹ J. Elkind, 'Energy Security: Call for A Broader Agenda' in C Pascual and J Elkind, *Energy Security, Economics, Politics, Strategies and Implications* (Brookings Institution's Press 2010) 121

Energy security as a crucial component of any energy policy entails the uninterrupted availability of energy resources at an affordable price in addition to being reliable and accessible.¹²

Energy security should not just entail making energy available, affordable, reliable and accessible; but also ensuring that its production, distribution and consumption support environmental standards. Many countries are making attempts towards designing appropriate policies to address energy security challenges and environmental sustainability.¹³

The definition of energy security has been expanded and referred to “four As” availability, affordability, accessibility and acceptability. Meaning, energy is available in sufficient amount at sufficiently-low prices, with all citizens having access to energy with minimized negative impacts that is acceptable to customers. Sovacool and Mukherjee introduced the five-dimension definition of energy security as: availability, affordability, technology development, sustainability and regulation.¹⁴

2.3. Security of supply

This is the measure put or guaranteed to ensure that there is physical access to certain fuel for continuous generation of electricity, gas, and fuel.¹⁵ It is a legal measure which guarantees adequate supplies of petroleum resources for domestic consumption in a reliable, affordable and sustainable ways. Also, it is a system or a measure put in place to ensure that there is a continuous flow of energy supply to meet demand and supply conditions.

Security of supply tends to tackle and avoid issues of disruption to energy supply by adopting to emergencies, meeting the flexibility of demand, ensuring consistency in sufficient supply.

Security of supply is the main pillar to energy security and a major concern to the societies.¹⁶ In that where energy is interrupted or not adequately supplied there can be no security to energy. Vis-à-vis where there is a hiccup in the security to the existing energy there would be no energy supply.

3.0. Legal framework

3.1. Convention of the African Energy Commission

This Convention provides for the establishment of the Energy Commission in Art 2. It further provides guideline to States to co-operate in the development of energy resources and the identification and promotion of regional and sub-regional projects in Art 3(b), sustainable and environmentally sound energy Art 3(c). Promote energy transfer technology, harmonize standard procedures in energy sector.

3.2. Revised African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources 2013

Art XIII provides that states shall endeavor to harmonize their policies, in particular within the framework of relevant conventions to which they are Parties. Art XII (2)(c) States shall monitor the state of their natural resources as well as the impact of development activities and projects upon such resources.

3.3. Africa Bioenergy Policy Framework and Guidelines 2013

The main objectives of this Framework and Guidelines are to (a) build a consensus on a shared framework that inspires and provides guidance to individual countries in developing policies and regulations; and (b) enhance awareness among African leaders and the civil society about the need for environmentally friendly and socially responsible bioenergy development policies.

4.0. Institutional framework

4.1. African Union Commission

The African Union (AU) is a continental body consisting of the 55 member states that make up the countries of the African Continent. It was officially launched in 2002 as a successor to the Organisation of

¹² International Energy Agency [IEA] Report on World Energy Outlook. (2014), How will Global Energy Market Evolve to 2040. Available from: <http://www.worldenergyoutlook.org/media/weowebsite>.

¹³ Opeyemi E. Akinyemi et al, Energy Security, Trade and Transition to Green Economy in Africa’ International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy, 2017, 7(3), 127-136.

¹⁴ B Sovacool and I Mukherjee, ‘Conceptualizing and measuring energy security: A synthesized approach (2011) DOI:[10.1016/j.energy.2011.06.043](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2011.06.043)

¹⁵ L Hancher and S. Janseen, ‘Shared Competences and Multifaceted Concepts-European Legal Frameworks for Security of Supply’ in B Barton, C Redgwell, A Ronne, and DN Zillman (eds), Energy Security: Managing Risks in a Dynamic Legal and Regulatory Environment (OUP 2004)

¹⁶ S M Goldberg, ‘Security of Supply in the Context of the European Energy Market Liberalization: A Brief Overview’ [2011] *International Business Law Journal* 443, 447

African Unity (OAU, 1963-1999).¹⁷ African Union (AU) Agenda 2063, Titled: “*Let There be Light: Harnessing Next-Generation Batteries for Africa's Energy Needs*” the African Union High-Level Panel on Emerging Technologies (APET) recommends that AU Member States embrace the utilization of renewable resources for electricity generation.¹⁸

4.2. African Energy Commission

The African Energy Commission (AFREC) is a continental specialized energy agency of the African Union (AU), under the Commission for Infrastructure and Energy, in charge of coordinating, harmonizing, protecting, conserving, developing, rational exploitation, commercializing and integrating energy resources on the African continent.¹⁹ The Energy Commission is focused on the following programs; Energy Transition Program, Energy Efficiency Program, Bioenergy program and oil and gas program.

4.3. African Development Bank:

The African Development Bank (AfDB) Group’s mission is to help reduce poverty, improve living conditions for Africans and mobilize resources for the continent’s economic and social development.²⁰ The AfDB has been involved in the extractive industries (EI) sector including the oil and gas sub-sector for nearly three decades.

5.0. Natural Resources in Africa for Energy Security

5.1. Oil and Gas

Africa is well endowed with oil and gas with 9.5% of global crude oil reserves and 8% of gas reserves are in Africa. In 2005, 12% of global production came from Africa, but the region only consumes 3.4% of global oil. Africa’s share of global gas consumption is only 2%. Oil and gas resources are concentrated in a relatively small number of countries and sub-regions (North and Western Africa).²¹ Africa consumes only but a little percentage of her oil and gas produce but exports a huge percentage that ought to be utilized. This is propelled by the inability for most of the African countries to have a refining facility.

Africa’s is set with the potential at producing about 1,273 billion bbl of oil (including condensate gas from gas extraction) and 82 tcm of natural gas (including associated gas from oil extraction) and estimates that it would be “technically and economically feasible” to recover around 381 billion bbl of oil and 73.8 tcm of gas.²²

5.2. Renewable energy

Africa is rich in renewable energy resources, including abundant sunlight, strong winds, and geothermal energy. However, the continent faces various challenges hindering the widespread adoption of clean energy sources. The continent has the lowest rate of electricity access in the world, leaving over 640 million Africans without reliable energy sources.²³

African countries are gifted with a huge—and still untapped—renewable energy potential. Estimates of power generation potential in the continent are 350 GW for hydroelectric, 110 GW for wind, 15 GW for

¹⁷ <https://au.int/en/overview>

¹⁸ AUDA-NEPAD, ‘Let there be Light: Harnessing Next-Generation Batteries for Africa's Energy Needs’ <https://www.nepad.org/publication/let-there-be-light-harnessing-next-generation-batteries-africas-energy-needs> accessed 29 October, 2025

¹⁹ <https://au-afrec.org/>

²⁰ <https://www.devex.com/organizations/african-development-bank-afdb-19838> accessed 29 October, 2025

²¹ AfDB/AU Study, Oil and Gas in Africa: A Prospective Study (2007) https://www.afdb.org/fileadmin/uploads/afdb/Documents/Generic-Documents/0199_EN_OIL%20AND%20GAS%20IN%20AFRICA%20A%20PROSPECTIVE%20STUDY.ppt#:~:text=Africa%20is%20well%20endowed%20with,gas%20reserves%20are%20in%20Africa.

²² Modelevsky MS, Modelevsky MM (2016) Assessment of the discovered and undiscovered oil and gas of Africa. *Russ Geol Geophys* 57:1342–1348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rgg.2016.08.019>

²³ AUDA-NEPAD, ‘Empowering Africa: Enhancing Access To Electricity Through Renewable Energy’ (2024) https://www.nepad.org/blog/empowering-africa-enhancing-access-electricity-through-renewable-energy#_ftn8 accessed 29 October, 2025

geothermal and a staggering 1000 GW for solar.²⁴ Africa is endowed naturally with solar energy, having a high sunshine.

5.3. Coal

Over 15 African countries produce coal as a natural resource with about 85% of the total coal recovery from South Africa, the fifth largest coal producer in the world. Domestically, coal is predominantly used for electricity generation, and also for liquid fuels, metallurgy, and industrial power.

5.4. Uranium

Nuclear energy can substitute for natural gas as well as for the oil- and diesel-fired generators that continue to be used, intermittently, in much of the developing world. These transitions are seen as appealing because they would relieve some of the demand pressures on global oil resources. A shift to nuclear power would also increase energy security by diversifying consumer states' primary energy bases.²⁵ Nuclear energy is a climate-friendly source of electricity.²⁶ Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Hungary, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden and Ukraine all get 30% or more of their electricity from nuclear reactors. The USA has about 90 reactors operating, supplying 20% of its electricity. France gets about 70% of its electricity from uranium.

Namibia holds about 7 per cent of the world's uranium reserves, which is mined by multinational companies and used to fuel nuclear power stations around the world.²⁷

5.0. Challenges to Energy security in Africa

1. High level of debt: Africa is overly indebted to other countries. This has affected some of the countries with low public funds to make due and proper investment in energy infrastructure. The high debt servicing cost discourages investment, limits domestic energy production. Further it makes the country to be vulnerable to foreign market prices and largely dependent on imports. Nigeria, South Africa, Egypt and other African countries are struggling with high debts thereby diverting their minds from energy investment and development but to payment of debt.
2. Political sentiment and corruption: Corruption is one of many serious challenges which undermine the effectiveness of institutions and entire governments in many African countries. Thus, corruption makes the business environment not very receptive to innovative green investment initiatives. The control of corruption can help countries leapfrog from low energy-efficient states and converge to high energy-efficient states.²⁸
3. Lack of sustainable development
4. Mismanagement of public facilities: Governments have always seen public facilities and utilities as an avenue or medium for political patronage. There by making the facilities a failed and incompetent facilities. A typical example is the mismanagement of the Keyan owned utilities to manage her renewable energy.
5. Over dependence on imported fuels

6.0. CONCLUSION

Energy security is the ability of the end user to utilize energy supply that is usable for the desired energy services. That is to say, that achieving energy security in Africa entails the ability for the end users such as households, public services and production users gain or have a reliable, affordable and uninterrupted access to energy either for daily domestic consumption or by way of electricity. From the research it is evident that Africa has undermined and underutilized her natural resources that is meant to carter her

²⁴ African Development Bank (2017) The new deal on energy for Africa. A transformative partnership to light up and power Africa by 2025. Update of implementation. https://www.afdb.org/fileadmin/uploads/afdb/Documents/Generic-Documents/Brochure_New_Deal_2_red.pdf. accessed 29 october, 2025

²⁵ n.1

²⁶ IAEA (2010a) *International Status and Prospects of Nuclear Power* (Vienna: International Atomic Energy Agency).

²⁷ World Nuclear Association, 'Emerging Nuclear Energy Countries' (World Nuclear Association)

²⁸ C D Akorli and P K Adom, 'The role of corruption control and regulatory quality in energy efficiency transition tendencies in Africa' *iScience*, 2023 (26) 3

energy demands. A key challenge is the coming together as a continent to achieve a common goal with all focus devoid of sentiments and propagandas.

7.0. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Leverage on natural gas: Africa has more gas and so, needs to switch from the use of coal to natural gas. This is because natural gas emits small amount of carbon dioxide as compared to fossil fuel or coal. Also, gas can be used in dual purpose. That is, it can be used domestically and also as revenue for export. Diversification into LPG and CNG.
2. Infrastructural development: Infrastructural developments have the abilities to sustain energy especially in rural areas with inadequate generation capacity, transmission and distribution channels. This includes building of mini grids that will be able to meet up with local demands and consumer's friendly in purchase.
3. Collaboration: There is the need for the institutions and other development agencies in Africa to work in synergy. The essence is to complement in the development and partnership intervention in the energy security and supply system. Also, States should come together to ensure that the African institutions are complimented as well. An example of collaboration is the West African Pipeline Project between Nigeria, Ghana, Togo and Benin Republic. More of this intervention approach will aid achieving energy security in Africa.
4. Policy framework: The regulations and policies in Africa should be strengthened to attract energy investment, development, guidelines for environmental impact, implementation and enforcement. A framework that will establish private capital, create an environment for both private and public investors. This is applicable to the African State, to make regulations that will foster the aim of energy conservation and security.
5. Human capital development: Africa needs to ensure that an intentional approach to human capacity development and putting the capacity to work. Trainings, workshops and other forms of capacity development that will promote energy efficiency and supply must be actively adopted.
6. Funding: The cumulative volume of the AfDB lending in the oil and gas sector only represents a very small share of the Bank's total lending. There is the need for more funding in the energy sector in Africa. This can be achieved through AfDB lending or financing energy projects. There should be financing through the public-private partnership models.
7. Improved accountability and transparency: A lack of accountability and transparency in several African countries, leading to widespread corruption, furthers energy insecurity. This is particularly true in oil-producing countries, which suffer from the so-called "oil curse."²⁹

²⁹ E T Young, 'Effective governance can help Africa capitalize on energy opportunities' *Concordiam Journal of European security and defense Issues* <https://perconcordiam.com/africas-energy-security/> accessed 29 October, 2025